

1 **A probable function for NLRP10 at the cell membrane in a ion channel-containing, calcium**
2 **signaling system associated with phospholipids.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730
6 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

7 Efforts towards understanding the complex cellular milieu in which lesser understood NLR family sensors
8 like NLRP10 operate in humans are complicated, in large part due to a lack of available experimental
9 approaches. We previously described a function for NLRP10 in sensing of cellular speed or velocity
10 suggesting existence of complex biochemical or biophysical processes receiving feedback from the cell
11 cycle that inform NLRP10 activation. We combined study of dendritic cells from NLRP10- deficient mice
12 with systems biologic analysis of NLRP10 transcriptional co-regulation patterns to discover
13 NLRP10-associated cellular machinery. We describe here a probable function for NLRP10 at the cell
14 membrane, associated with plasma membrane phospholipids and ion channels in a signaling system that
15 utilizes calcium flux. The NLRP10 signaling system was associated with transient receptor potential
16 vanilloid (TRPV) channels.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28